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Showcase “Electricity imports”

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Where do Germany's Electricity imports come from? Publication of extended data and supplementary material in the Leibniz Data Manager in NFDI4Energy

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General Information

Summary

The conference proceedings article “Where do Germany’s electricity imports come from?” for the 21st International Conference on the European Energy Market 2025 discusses different measures to estimate the origin of Germany’s electricity imports. This topic has regularly been subject of discussions in the public debate, for instance framed in the context of an alleged German dependence of imported French nuclear power. The supplementary material published in the Leibniz Data Manager contains full results data (time series for all measures for several years) and supplementary material (additional explanations of all measures), thus providing a significant benefit beyond the published article.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The Leibniz Data Manager is a service provided by NFDI4Energy which allows to upload, download and organize datasets along with their metadata. Whereas in Task Area 8 the development and provisioning of services is organized, in Task Area 6 use cases and show case are collected.

Deliverable (Showcase description)

Internal Documentation

Title: Where do Germany's Electricity imports come from? Publication of extended data and supplementary material in the Leibniz Data Manager in NFDI4Energy

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Abstract:

The conference proceedings article for the 21st International Conference on the European Energy Market 2025 discusses different measures to estimate the origin of Germany's electricity imports. This topic has regularly been subject of discussions in the public debate, for instance framed in the context of an alleged German dependence of imported French nuclear power. The supplementary material published in the Leibniz Data Manager contains full results data (time series for all measures for several years) and supplementary material (additional explanations of all measures), thus providing a significant benefit beyond the published article.

Links

Conference paper: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11050092>

Conference paper (free preprint): <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.20232>

LDM entry: <https://doi.org/10.71694/0etrciri>

NFDI4Energy input:

Leibniz data manager in NFDI4Energy

TAs involved:

TA2, TA4, TA6, TA8

Energy research:

The research article analyses the methodological challenges of determining the origin of Germany's electricity imports within the interconnected European market. The authors compare different calculation methods—from using scheduled commercial flows to physical power flow tracing—and demonstrate that the determined volume and origin of imports vary significantly depending on the chosen approach. The study concludes that there is no single, definitive answer to where imports come from and recommends that analyses be transparent about the specific methods used.

Meta level:

This research provides a clear motivation for using a dedicated data publication service for the following reasons:

- **Insufficient space in the published article:** The original journal article did not have enough space to include detailed descriptions of the different analytical measures used, which suggests the publication of more extensive supplementary material.

- **Availability of additional data:** The published article only presented result data for a single year, even though results for several other years were available and valuable for comparison.
- **Greater data granularity:** The article focused on annual aggregated data, but the underlying research generated hourly time-series for all measures, which contain significantly more detail.
- **Public interest:** The topic is frequently discussed in media and on social media platforms, highlighting the need for easily accessible data that does not require an API, a login, or a complicated download process. An interactive visualization of the data is a useful tool for immediate understanding and for creating figures that could be used directly in public discussions.
- **Updated data:** The data publication service allows to update the data with more recent results also after publication of the research article.
- **Methodological transparency:** While other institutions also provide data on electricity imports, its interpretation can be challenging due to different input data and applied approaches. This creates a need for greater transparency regarding the underlying data and methodologies, which can be addressed by sharing detailed documentation and full result datasets.

Enhancement:

To improve upon the original publication, all results data, extensive supplementary material, and additional result data have been published in the Leibniz Data Manager (LDM). Furthermore, the dataset was updated with the most recent available data in January 2026. When discussing the research at the NFDI4Energy conference, the EEM2025 conference, and in posts on LinkedIn, the link to the LDM has always been communicated to give access to all data and supplementary material. The dataset has been used and referenced to in the recent monitoring report "[Monitoringbericht 2025](#)" of the "Expertenkommission zum Energiewende-Monitoring".

Potential testimonials:

Christoph Maurer, Consentec (public comment regarding the relevance of the research after publication)

Lukas Jany, Umweltbundesamt (used data for own work when comparing origin of imports based on markets, physical flows, and guarantees of origin)

Lessons learned:

Observations from this showcase indicate that the Leibniz Data Manager's visualization feature is most useful for result data rather than large bulk data. Careful data preparation is required for the visualization to function as intended. During the data integration process, a feature to visualize filtered data was implemented upon suggestion. It was also noted that the ability to ignore most metadata fields during submission can serve as an easy entry into the data publication process.

Brief sections for the website

The Showcase's Starting Point in Energy System Research

A research article by NFDI4Energy members examined the methodological challenges of determining the origin of Germany's electricity imports within the interconnected European market. The authors compare different calculation methods and demonstrate that the determined volume and origin of imports vary significantly depending on the chosen approach. The study concludes that there is no single, definitive answer to where imports come from and recommends that analyses be transparent about the specific methods used.

Motivation and Research Requirements

The publication of the original research article did not allow detailed descriptions of the analytical measures or the inclusion of underlying data, which suggests publishing supplementary material on an external platform. Since the topic is frequently discussed not only by experts, but a wider audience, the material should be easily accessible, ideally with direct visualization features for selected result data.

NFDI4Energy Solution

The complete results data, supplementary material, and additional datasets were published in the Leibniz Data Manager (LDM), which is part of the NFDI4Energy service portfolio. Furthermore, the dataset was later updated with the most recent available data. The data visualization feature included in the LDM has been used by the authors when explaining the results to data journalists or in discussions with colleagues from the German Government Environmental Agency.